

Determination of Water-Soluble Vitamin Content in Selected Vegetables and Fruits

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to determine the amounts of water-soluble vitamins [thiamine hydrochloride (B₁), riboflavin (B₂), nicotinic acid (B₃), pantothenic acid (B₅), pyridoxine hydrochloride (B₆), folic acid (B₉) and vitamin C] in some vegetables and fruits using HPLC.

It was determined that vitamin B₁ in vegetables and fruits ranged from 0.09±0.01 to 19.00±1.7 µg/g, vitamin B₂ from 0.12±0.01 to 5.80±0.51 µg/g, and vitamins B₃, B₅, and B₆ in the same samples ranged from 0.52±0.04 to 101.00±9.30 µg/g, 0.43±0.03 to 49.60±4.40 µg/g, and 0.41±0.03 to 180±17 µg/g, respectively. Vitamins B₉ and C ranged from 0.09±0.01 to 150.00±14.00 µg/g and 35.00±3.00 to 1593.00±121.00 µg/g, respectively.

Our findings suggest that the majority of fruits and vegetables are sufficiently rich in water-soluble vitamins.

Keywords: Vitamin B₁, B₂, B₃, B₅, B₆, B₉, C, fruit and vegetable

1. Introduction

Vitamins can be divided into two main groups: water-soluble and fat-soluble. The majority of water-soluble vitamins make up the B complex. In fact, the term B complex refers to all known essential water-soluble vitamins, except vitamin C. B vitamins function as follows: thiamine (B₁), riboflavin (B₂), niacin (B₃), pantothenic acid (B₅), pyridoxine (B₆), biotin (B₇), folate (B₉), and cobalamin (B₁₂). B vitamins act as coenzymes in various enzymatic processes, including important functions in the brain and nervous system [1]. Specifically, the active forms of thiamine, riboflavin, niacin, and pantothenic acid function in the electron transport chain of the citric acid cycle. Consequently, they form essential coenzymes in mitochondrial aerobic respiration and cellular energy production through their direct role in the formation of adenosine triphosphate (ATP), the cell's energy unit. Acetyl-CoA containing pantothenic acid provides the main substrate for this cycle [2]. B vitamins have reciprocal contributions to the citric acid cycle and the electron transport chain, a central catabolic process in mitochondria [3].

Vitamin C is one of the essential, water-soluble vitamins required for the normal metabolic functions of the human body. It exists in two biologically active forms: L-ascorbic acid and L-dehydroascorbic acid. Both forms exhibit vitamin C activity. L-ascorbic acid is readily oxidized to DHA, which can then be reduced back to ascorbic acid. This occurs through the transfer of electrons, due to vitamin C's ability to act as an electron donor (reducing agent or antioxidant) for other molecules. This reducing role of vitamin C explains many of its biochemical and molecular functions in the body [4], [5].

Vitamin deficiency causes serious illnesses, metabolic disorders in humans, even though only small concentrations are needed to maintain good health, and this can lead to disease or even death [6], [7].

As is known, vitamins are natural components of foods, and a balanced diet provides all the necessary vitamins. Water-soluble vitamins, which play an important role in catabolic and anabolic metabolism, are excreted in the urine. Since these vitamins are not stored in the body, they need to be consumed daily. Therefore, it is necessary to know which foods are rich in vitamins. For this reason, the study aimed to determine the levels of seven water-soluble vitamins—thiamine hydrochloride (B₁), riboflavin (B₂), nicotinic acid (B₃), pantothenic acid (B₅), pyridoxine hydrochloride (B₆), folic acid (B₉), and vitamin C in commonly consumed fruits and vegetables.

2. Material and Methods

Fresh vegetables and fruits obtained from the market were wrapped in aluminium foil, kept in the refrigerator at 4°C, and analysed within a maximum of 1 days. For the analyses, 1.0–2.0 g of the thoroughly homogenized samples was taken into PVC tubes, and 0.5 mL of 1.0 M HClO₄ was added to each tube. After vortexing, the total volume was made up to 5 mL with distilled water, and the mixture was incubated in an ultrasonic water bath at room temperature for 10 minutes. It was then centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 10 minutes, and the supernatant was carefully transferred to 1.0 mL HPLC vials. The studies were performed using HPLC (SHIMADZU Prominence-I LC-2030C 3D Model PDA detector) on a Supelcosil LC-18-DB column (150 mm - 4.6 mm ID; 5 µm) at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min, with methanol-5 mM heptane sulfonic acid sodium salt 0.1% triethylamine (TEA) (25:75 v/v); pH 2.8 mobile phase.

Vitamins B₁, B₂, B₃, and B₅ were determined at 260 nm, vitamin B₆ and vitamin B₉ at 290 nm, and vitamin C at 245 nm wavelength [8], [9].

2.1. Statistical analysis

All measurements were made in three parallels, and the results were given as Mean ± Standard deviation and statistical significance was expressed as p<0.05.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the amounts of vitamins B₁, B₂, B₃, B₅, B₆, B₉, and C in some vegetables and fruits. However, among the general public, all of these researched materials are referred to as vegetables.

As shown in Table 1, among the vegetables examined, cabbage and lettuce were relatively poor in vitamins, while sorrel and rhubarb were richer. Similarly, among fruits, cucumber and eggplant were relatively poor in vitamins, while peas and tomato were richer.

Vitamin B₁ is a coenzyme in the pentose phosphate pathway, an essential step in the synthesis of aromatic amino acid precursors of fatty acids, steroids, nucleic acids, various neurotransmitters, and other bioactive compounds necessary for brain function [10].

The lowest B₁ content in the examined vegetables and fruits was found in radish and eggplant, respectively while the highest amounts were found in rhubarb and tomato, respectively.

Vitamin B₂ undergoes phosphorylation to produce Flavin mononucleotide (FMN), which is then broken down into Flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD). As cofactors in energy metabolism, FMN and FAD are essential for coenzyme function in various oxidation and reduction reactions in all aerobic life forms [11].

Table 1. Vitamin B and C contents of various fruits and vegetables.

Fruit / Veritable	Vitamins ($\mu\text{g/g}$)						
	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₅	B ₆	B ₉	C
Carrot*	0.68±0.04	0.58±0.03	7.50±0.54	3.90±0.32	4.64±0.38	0.18±0.01	98±90
Black carrot*	0.52±0.04	0.34±0.02	12.11±1.04	3.2±0.28	3.72±0.30	0.16±0.01	105±90
Cabbage*	0.47±0.04	0.33±0.25	3.90±0.32	2.2±0.18	0.6±0.05	0.45±0.03	353±28
Red cabbage*	0.53±0.04	2.9±0.23	16.94±1.42	2.4±0.18	1.9±0.13	0.92±0.07	982±83
Fresh mint*	1.08±0.08	3.43±0.28	16.29±1.48	4.26±0.36	3.92±0.32	1.19±0.1	262±21
Parsley*	1.89±0.15	1.97±0.16	21.85±1.82	2.40±0.19	1.62±0.12	1.76±0.13	1593±12
Green onion leaf*	0.51±0.04	0.64±0.05	2.38±0.18	0.43±0.03	0.57±0.04	0.62±0.05	242±18
Dry onion*	0.71±0.06	0.48±0.03	6.76±0.55	0.72±0.06	1.42±0.11	0.4±0.03	79±70
Spinach*	0.56±0.04	1.06±0.09	2.11±0.15	2.54±0.2	1.20±0.1	2.28±0.19	354±26
Radish*	0.35±0.03	0.35±0.03	2.35±0.19	0.82±0.07	0.90±0.08	1.1±0.09	201±17
Dill*	0.61±0.05	1.28±0.11	8.52±0.76	1.76±0.15	0.95±0.09	1.41±0.11	302±26
Lettuce*	0.39±0.03	0.34±0.03	1.84±0.15	1.12±0.1	0.64±0.05	1.36±0.11	65.00±60
Purslane*	0.66±0.06	4.16±0.38	17.52±1.51	0.82±0.07	2.71±0.23	0.7±0.06	248±20
Cress*	2.10±0.18	4.90±0.42	18.94±1.81	0.64±0.05	3.31±0.28	1.20±0.11	835±75
Sorrel*	2.34±0.20	5.38±0.48	13.23±1.24	0.71±0.06	3.44±0.29	3.61±0.30	870±78
Arugula *	0.95±0.08	1.92±0.18	13.56±1.29	3.60±0.31	1.88±0.17	8.23±0.77	1085±91
Leek*	0.66±0.05	0.69±0.06	4.13±0.37	1.50±0.14	1.54±0.14	0.56±0.05	218±19
Potato*	0.54±0.04	0.41±0.03	0.52±0.04	2.68±0.22	16.4±1.54	0.12±0.01	235±21
Garlic*	1.25±0.10	0.69±0.06	10.28±0.95	1.06±0.09	13.04±1.20	0.46±0.40	116±10
Broccoli*	0.55±0.04	0.58±0.05	2.86±0.22	2.26±0.19	0.75±0.07	1.49±0.13	996±89
vine leaf*	3.66±0.30	0.66±0.06	1.67±0.16	0.51±0.04	4.51±0.41	2.1±0.19	570±51
Cauliflower*	0.38±0.03	0.57±0.05	3.36±0.29	3.59±0.31	6.40±0.59	1.0±0.10	450±41
Rhubarb*	19.00±1.7	2.38±0.19	73.47±6.96	2.90±0.23	180.00±17	6.32±0.56	290±24
Cucumber**	0.43±0.04	0.49±0.04	1.78±0.16	2.6±0.22	0.51±0.04	0.12±0.09	119±9
Squash**	0.56±0.04	0.46±0.03	5.20±0.35	1.10±0.09	0.90±0.08	0.09±0.01	154±13
Fresh bean**	0.58±0.04	0.83±0.07	2.95±0.23	0.46±0.03	0.47±0.04	0.39±0.03	156±14
Peas**	3.04±0.28	1.19±0.10	9.58±0.88	0.52±0.04	5.56±0.50	0.63±0.05	476±42
Green pepper**	0.61±0.05	0.49±0.05	4.53±0.40	3.1±0.28	3.95±0.35	0.36±0.30	1451±11
Red pepper**	0.66±0.06	0.42±0.03	3.60±0.32	0.73±0.06	1.28±0.11	0.13±0.01	797±53
Tomato**	7.54±0.70	5.80±0.51	101±9.30	49.6±4.40	17.92±1.60	150.00±14	389±36
Eggplant**	0.09±0.01	0.12±0.01	2.89±0.22	1.17±0.10	0.41±0.03	0.23±0.02	35±3.0
Strawberry**	0.38±0.03	0.57±0.05	1.04±0.01	1.21±0.10	3.75±0.32	0.30±0.02	306±27

Plants that are botanically classified as vegetables (*) and fruits (***) are denoted accordingly

The lowest amounts of vitamin B₂ in vegetables and fruits were found in cabbage and eggplant, respectively while the highest amounts were found in sorrel and tomato.

Vitamin B₃, is a precursor to NAD and NADP, which are cofactors for many enzymes in the body. There are numerous redox reactions in which NAD and NADH are converted into each other. This vitamin plays a vital role in human health by facilitating energy synthesis and supporting antioxidant defense mechanisms [12].

The lowest amounts of vitamin B₃ in vegetables and fruits were found in potato and strawberry, respectively, while the highest amounts were found in rhubarb and tomato.

Vitamin B₅ is a substrate for the synthesis of the commonly found CoA. Besides its role in oxidative metabolism. Vitamin B5 contributes to the structure and function of brain cells through its role in the

synthesis of CoA. Cholesterol, amino acids, phospholipids, and fatty acids. Its contribution to the endocrine system, particularly in hormone synthesis and regulation, is equally important [13].

In terms of vitamin B5 content, the poorest vegetables and fruits are green onion leaves and fresh bean, respectively, while the richest are fresh mint and tomato.

Vitamin B₆ acts as a catalyst in a number of important biochemical reactions, including protein metabolism, nervous system functions, red blood cell production. immune system strengthening, and hormonal balance. Additionally, vitamin B₆ plays a role in the synthesis of neurotransmitters such as serotonin, norepinephrine, and dopamine [14].

The vegetables and fruits poorest in vitamin B₆ are green onion leaves and eggplant, respectively while the richest are rhubarb and tomato.

Vitamin B₉ is known in its active form as tetrahydrofolate (THF). B₉ plays a vital role in a number of cellular reactions known as folate-mediated single-carbon metabolism, including DNA synthesis. DNA and RNA modifications, red blood cell production and metabolism of amino acids necessary for cell division, and the synthesis of amino acids and nucleic acids [15].

The vegetables and fruits poorest in vitamin B₉ are potato and squash, respectively, while the richest are arugula and tomato.

Vitamin C acts as an electron donor for numerous enzymes involved in collagen biosynthesis, peptide amidation, tyrosine metabolism, carnitine biosynthesis, and catecholamine biosynthesis. It is also a potent antioxidant and has been shown to protect lipids in human plasma from oxidative damage. It contributes to the conservation of reduced glutathione (GSH) and the regeneration of α -tocopherol. Vitamin C is known to scavenge nitrosating agents and inhibit the formation of potentially mutagenic N-nitroso compounds [16].

The lowest amounts of vitamin C in fruits and vegetables are found in lettuce and eggplant, respectively while the highest amounts are found in parsley and green pepper.

Uğur et al. (5) found in their research that the amounts of vitamin C in red pepper, broccoli, green pepper, red cabbage, tomato and strawberry are consistent with our findings.

Mina et al. (17) determined the amounts of vitamins B₁, B₂, B₆ and C in beans, eggplant, carrots, green peppers, onions, potatoes and tomatoes. For example, they found the amounts of vitamins B₁, B₂, B₆ and C in green peppers to be 0.034, 0.050, 0,23, 102.267 mg/100g, respectively. They also reported that the amounts of vitamins B₁, B₂, B₆, and C in potatoes were 0.081, 0.093, 0.277, and 19.067 mg/100g, respectively. Their findings are consistent with our results.

Karatas et al. (18) reported that the vitamin B₉ in dry onions, carrots, lettuce, cauliflower, parsley, cucumbers and spinach were 133, 140, 395, 560, 640, 280 and 658 ng/g, respectively.

It can be said that our findings are consistent with the findings of Karatas et al. (18).

Ismail and her friends (19) found the amounts of vitamins B₁, B₂, B₃, B₆ and B₉ in carrots to be 0.02, 0.02, 0.016, 0.06 and 0.19 mg / 100 g respectively, and the amounts in spinach to be 0.08, 0.1, 0.01, 0.26 and 0.12 mg / 100 g respectively. It can be said that their findings are consistent with our findings.

Kasim and Kasim (20) determined the amounts of vitamins C, B₁, B₂, B₃, B₆ and B₉ in samples of tomatoes, red peppers, eggplants, carrots, radishes, cabbage and strawberries. For example, they reported that the amounts of vitamins C, B₁, B₂, B₃, B₆ and B₉ in tomatoes were 19.8, 0.03, 0.025, 0.613, 0.076 and 13 mg/100

g respectively, and in radishes they were 19.2, 0.031, 0.018, 0.249, 0.055 and 117 mg/100 g respectively. It can be said that the results in the literature are consistent with our findings.

In some cases, the presence of vitamin values that do not conform to the literature can be explained by differences in the harvesting times and geographical conditions of the samples.

4. Conclusion and Suggestions

The water-soluble vitamin content of fruits and vegetables consumed raw or cooked was compared. Considering that water-soluble vitamins are degraded by heat and pass into the cooking water. changes in vitamin content depending on cooking and storage conditions can be investigated.

Conflict of Interest

Author declares that there is no known conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Kennedy, D.O., B vitamins and the brain: Mechanisms. dose and efficacy--A Review. *Nutrients*. 2016. 8(2): p. 68.
- [2] Kerns, J.C., C. Arundel, L.S. Chawla, Thiamin deficiency in people with obesity. *Advances in Nutrition*. 2015. 6(2): p. 147-153.
- [3] Huskisson, E., Maggini, S.M. Ruf, The role of vitamins and minerals in energy metabolism and well-being. *Journal of International Medical Research*. 2007. 35: p. 277-289.
- [4] Carr, A.C., S. Maggini, Vitamin C and Immune Function. *Nutrients*. 2017. 9: p. 1-25.
- [5] Uğur, H., S. Eker, J. Çatak, M. Yaman, Vitamin C and Effect on Diseases. *European Journal of Science and Technology*. 2020. 19: p. 746-756.
- [6] Combs Jr, G.F., Discovery of the vitamins. in: *The Vitamins: Fundamental Aspects in Nutrition and Health*. Academic Press. Inc. San Diego. 1992. p. 9.
- [7] Zheng, F., P. He, Analysis of Differences in the Serum Levels of Various Vitamins During Pregnancy: Effects of Gestational Stage and Age. *Clinical and Experimental Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 2024. 51(7): p. 152.
- [8] Amidzic, R., J. Brboric, O. Cudina, S. Vladimirov, RP-HPLC Determination of vitamins B₁, B₃, B₆, folic acid and B₁₂ in multivitamin tablets. *Journal of the Serbian Chemical Society*. 2005. 70(10): p.1229–1235.
- [9] Ali, H.M., F. Karataş, D. Özer, S. Saydam, Element and water-soluble vitamins profile of *Rhus coriaria* L. (sumac) grown in different regions. *Biological Trace Element Research*. 2024. 202: p. 3293-3302.
- [10] Hirsch, J.A., J. Parrott, New considerations on the neuromodulatory role of thiamine. *Pharmacology*. 2012. 89: p. 111-116.
- [11] Lienhart, W.D., V. Gudipati, P. Macheroux, The human flavoproteome. *Archives of Biochemistry and Biophysics*. 2013. 15: p. 150-162.
- [12] Maqbool, M.A., M. Aslam, W. Akbar, Z. Iqbal, Biological importance of vitamins for human health: A review. *Journal of Agriculture and Basic Science*. 2017. 2(3): p. 50-58.
- [13] Gheita, A.A., T.A. Gheita, S.A. Kenawy, The potential role of B5: A stitch in time and switch in cytokine. *Phytotherapy Research*. 2020. 34(2): p. 306-314.
- [14] Calderón - Ospina, C.A., M.O. Nava - Mesa, B vitamins in the nervous system: Current knowledge of the biochemical modes of action and synergies of thiamine. pyridoxine. and cobalamin. *CNS Neuroscience and Therapeutics*. 2020. 26: p. 5-13.

- [15] Lan, X., M.S. Field, P.J. Stover, Cell cycle regulation of folate mediated one-carbon metabolism. Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews Systems Biology and Medicine. 2018. 10(6): e1426.
- [16] Camarena, V., G. Wang, The epigenetic role of vitamin C in health and disease. Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences. 2016. 73(8): p. 1645-1658.
- [17] Mina, M., A.T. MA Rahim, Md. N. Haque, Md.S. Hossain Khan, Proximate and Water Soluble Vitamin Contents in Some Selected Bangladeshi Fruits and Vegetables. Journal of Scientific Research & Reports. 2016. 11(6): p. 1-8.
- [18] Karatas, F., A. Cansiz, H. Cifci, Z. Serbetci, Determination of folic acid level in some foodstuffs. Chemistry of Natural Compounds. 2007. 43(3): p.310-312
- [19] Ismail, F., F.N. Talpur, A.N. Memon, Determination of Water-Soluble Vitamin in Fruits and Vegetables Marketed in Sindh Pakistan. Pakistan Journal of Nutrition. 2013. 12(2): p.197-199
- [20] Kasim, R., M.U. Kasim, Composition of colorful fruits and vegetables and its importance for human health. 8th International Vocational Schools Symposium, UMYOS 19 Sinop. 2019: p.31-39